

INTERCULTURAL RELATIONS IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF SOCIETY

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Abstract: *In this thesis, the authors explore the factors that shape intercultural relations in society and underscore the pressing need for further research in this field.*

Keywords: intercultural dialogue; interaction of language and culture; functions of language and culture; political signs of interaction of language and culture.

Introduction

Social relations, a complex web that permeates all aspects of human life, are typically categorized into political, economic, social, and cultural spheres. Culture, in its broadest sense, encompasses all human activities: physiological, material, and spiritual (Frame A., 2017). However, in this context, we focus on the intricate interplay of language with the spiritual aspect of culture, as expressed through traditions, customs, and morality. This interaction is of profound significance in these areas (Harutyunyan K., 2011).

Method

The content of the interaction of language and culture should be understood as the language's service in the communication process between individuals (Lut K. & Starenkova H., 2022).

Secondly, according to social status, ordinary citizens or representatives of non-governmental organizations and state bodies belong to various national cultural figures that arise in the process of social relations in the field of culture. This means that communication through language includes individuals who define the semantic and symbolic boundaries of their respective cultures, not their own culture.

Communication through language, being carried out through individuals, provides the following opportunities:

- firstly, a rich culture contains many hidden possibilities that allow building a semantic bridge to another culture;
- secondly, a creative person can go beyond the limitations imposed by the original culture. Therefore, a person, being a cultural creator, can find a way to communicate with different cultures (Alimova Sh.D., 2016).

Results and Discussion

Based on this, it can be said that culture, unlike language, performs an establishing function since traditions and customs regulate social relations. That is, it creates social relations in society. Language has a specific feature in relation to culture: It serves as a service function, a necessary condition for communication, and through it ensures the emergence, change, and termination of social relations.

This trend in the development of intercultural relations leads to the need to consider the factors of intercultural communication, including the problem of interaction between language and culture, from three central positions:

- first is the interaction of language and culture within the framework of the same national-state subject. It has different national-cultural characteristics;

– secondly, the interaction of the language and culture of different nationalities and ethnic groups within the framework of a single state language;

– Third, different peoples' languages and cultures interact with each other.

For example, in the first case, in Uzbekistan, the interaction of the Uzbek and Karakalpak languages and cultures can serve ([Aytmuradov J.T., 2010](#)).

The second case, in Russia, involves the interaction of the national languages and cultures of, say, Buryatia, Dagestan, or Ingushetia when there is a Russian federal state language.

The third example is the interaction of the languages and cultures of the peoples of Uzbekistan, Russia, and Great Britain, each of which has national-state sovereignty.

Here, suppose the first two positions are more well-known and understandable. In that case, the third position is new and actively developing in many ways, expressed in the increased influence on changing the interaction of language and culture in the direction of universalization. Such a tendency to universalization arises based on the generalization of language and, through it, the culture of different peoples.

The language with universal properties also includes the Russian language, previously the state language of the former Soviet Union countries. It has not lost its importance as a language of international communication in the CIS countries. The volume of activity of the Russian language in the mass media of Uzbekistan also evidences this. In particular, along with the Uzbek language, a large language space is given to the Russian language on TV and radio channels, in print publications, and on the Internet.

Thus, the volume of broadcasts on television in Uzbek - 90.9%, in Russian - 9%, in English - 1% (1); on the radio in Uzbek – 99%, in Russian – 12%, in English – 5% (2); on websites: in Uzbek – 5%, in Russian – 90%, in English – 75%.

The three-stage space should include the emergence of the Uzbek language into English through Russian. At the same time, in modern times, in many cases, Uzbek

speakers learn English through Russian, leaving traces of both languages in themselves and, through the language, traces of their culture. At the same time, the number of Uzbeks who bypass Russian and mainly learn English directly is increasing. The increase in Uzbek-English and English-Uzbek dictionaries evidences this. Therefore, in connection with the increasing trend of Uzbek-English bilingualism and M.Z. According to Sadriddinova, “trilingual dictionaries can only be educational content; they are intended for bilingual schoolchildren and students who study a third language as an academic subject. For example, students of Uzbekistan who know their native language, speak the language of interethnic communication, and study English” lose their significance (Sadriddinova M.Z., 1984).

Conclusion

Based on all that has been said, the following conclusions can be drawn:

- firstly, two languages, Russian and English, have a significant impact on the Uzbek language and culture, with a tendency to increase the importance of English;
- secondly, within the framework of public education, the interaction of language and culture should be improved to the extent that it can provide all the actions in the field of culture in the human mind in the direction of language development;
- Third, improving intercultural interactions through international dialogue in the context of globalization should establish a beneficial balance for their functioning in the national language and cultural space and find forms and methods capable of ensuring this.

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MADANIYATLARARO MUNOSABATLARNING RIVOJLANISH TENDENTSIYALARI

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Annotatsiya: *Ushbu tezisdagi mualliflar jamiyat taraqqiyotida madaniyatlararo munosabatlarning rivojlanishi omillari to'xtalib o'tib, bu boradagi qilinishi kerak bo'lgan ishlarga o'z munosabatlarini bildirgan.*

Kalit so'zlar: madaniyatlararo muloqot; til va madaniyatning o'zaro ta'siri; til va madaniyat funktsiyalari; til va madaniyat o'zaro ta'sirining siyosiy belgilari.